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SOS Berlin Alexanderplatz: the razing of DDR Modernism

Introduction

In three dramatic periods of 20th century Germany - nazism, post-war and reunification - political, ideological and economic factors brought about large scale urban destruction and reconstruction of the pre-existing built environment of German cities, especially Berlin. In Nazi Germany, architecture was used by Hitler as an instrument of state propaganda and his plans to transform Berlin into Germania, the Capital of the Third Reich, imbued with a gigantic monumentalism expressing victory, domination and glory, if built, would have devastated the entire Berlin urban and architectural structure and skyline. (Cavalcanti: 1994; 1997)

Post-war Germany was a divided state controlled by Western and Eastern Allied occupiers. In Berlin, the post-war reconstruction was carried out according to antagonistic and conflictive urban and architectural principles which responded to political régimes ideologically opposed and with distinct economic priorities which brought about further destruction to the already shattered city's built environment, both in the west and east. This was aggravated with the construction of the Berlin Wall in 1961, the most celebrated political allegory of the Cold War, which turned Berlin into the nerve centre of the political, military and ideological confrontation between Eastern and Western Europe. In the *Deutsche Demokratische Republik-DDR* (the German Democratic Republic), both in the early years under Stalin's rule and later, with the de-Stalinization process installed by Nikita Krushchev, the politics of urban recon-

struction of the bombed cities were imbued with a strong ideological connotation in which architecture and urban design were used as powerful political weapons to express the new society and to pave the path to Socialism. (Cavalcanti & Brendle: 1998)

In East Berlin, *die Hauptstadt der DDR* (the capital of the German Democratic Republic), the National Programme of Reconstruction began only in 1951, but the first modernist buildings had already been designed in 1949, by Hans Scharoun's associate, Ludmilla Herzenstein, in the former Frankfurter Allee, renamed later Stalinallee. Then, the Socialist Realism in Eastern Europe imposed by the USSR during the Stalin Era, in the DDR as well as in all people's democracies, became the only accepted and correct language to express official ideology and the new political order in literature, art, architecture and urban planning. As a result, Functionalism and the Bauhaus were officially rejected and considered as an instrument of American imperialism and the clear expression of Western decadence.

The Stalinallee was turned into an ostentatious axis lined with oversized architectural structures decorated with pseudoclassical motifs setting a pattern for urban and architectural developments in the DDR, such as the Lange Strasse in Rostock and the Rossplatz in Leipzig. Modernism was to come again to the DDR and to East Berlin only after the death of Stalin in 1953 when the Stalinallee was renamed Karl-Marx-Allee.

In the *Bundesrepublik Deutschland* (the Federal Republic of Germany), Modernism was to express in architecture and city planning the western liberalism and democracy. The most spectacular answer to what was called "red classicism" of the east was the *Internationale Bauausstellung Berlin - Interbau*, which gathered in Hansaviertel, in West Berlin, the work of great masters of Modernism such as Walter Gropius, Le Corbusier, Oscar Niemeyer, Alvar Aalto, among many others.

In 1991, the reunification of the country which followed the collapse of Communism and the fall of the Berlin Wall in 1989, brought about further re-planning of Berlin, now as the Federal Capital of reunited Germany. Since then, government projects as well as megaprojects of private capital such as the Potsdamerplatz, Leipzigstrasse, Friedrichstrasse, Pariserplatz, etc., have launched a boom of reconstruction in the two former divided cities and attracted powerful investors and developers to what has been called "the biggest building site in Europe".

Alexanderplatz and its neighbouring building ensembles, an important architectural and urban heritage of DDR Modernism, are under threat. An international competition carried out in 1993 sponsored by the *Berliner Senat* and 8 private investors¹ set

the guidelines for a comprehensive redesign which is due to start in 2001. The first prize, by Hans Kollhof, calls for radical physical changes of the whole area and the demolition of most of the Modern buildings, except those by Behrens.

Alexanderplatz and the *Zentrale Achse* Berlin: Modernism in the *Hauptstadt der DDR*

Alexanderplatz or Alex, as it is called by Eastern Berliners, is Berlin's most complex urban place as it carries contradictory and conflictive political, ideological and affective messages and meanings for its citizens. In the classic Alfred Döblin's novel, *Berlin Alexanderplatz*, it is shown as a Berlin crucial point where the working class or the underground people used to meet. As one of the busiest traffic junctions in the city and a place which gathered a large variety of functions (working place, dwellings, private and government offices, public transport, trade, cultural and entertainment facilities, etc.), it underwent great urban and architectural changes throughout the 20th century² reflecting its urban, social and political history which have been determinant factors shaping its built form³.

The air raids of World War II left Berlin devastated. In Alexanderplatz, the only buildings which could be reconstructed were the Alexander and Berolina Haus, by Peter Behrens. The Resolution of the Council of Ministers of 7 July 1950 approved the „16 Principles of Urban Development“ which defined the urban planning guidelines for the reconstruction of East Berlin's centre, still during Walter Ulbricht's rule which was very much in line with Moscow's opposition to Modernism. Accordingly, „the most important and most monumental buildings were to be constructed in the city centre, dominating the architectural composition of urban planning and determining the architectural profile of the city“. (Flierl: 1998)

With the return of Modernism to the German Democratic Republic which followed the death of Stalin in 1953, the plan for the reconstruction of East Berlin as the capital of the DDR was conceived as a functional and aesthetical unity and consisted of a West-East structural axis of 3,6km stretching from Brandenburger Tor to Alexanderplatz (and later to Strausberger Platz), officially called *Zentrale Achse*, crossing at Alexanderplatz, along which the central government buildings or the political forum, civic places, as well as large dwellings complexes were set. By reducing building density, both residential and work-place, spacious green areas, wide streets and dispersed development granted better hygienic conditions allowing the city to breathe.

The planning of Alexanderplatz evolved from a Competition of Ideas for the Socialist Design of the

German Democratic Republic - 1958 /1960 and was carried out in connection with the road traffic restructuring of the inner city. From the very beginning the role of Alexanderplatz in the *Zentrale Achse* was clear: "to make intelligible (in visual terms) the unity of the axial relations, which converged from the West and from the South East to meet in the area of the square." (Tscheschner, 1993: 38) Alexanderplatz was also the main Eastern entrance to the city centre where the main roads converged, and a strategic point for a large public transport system composed of tram, underground and metropolitan railway. In 1963, the traffic at Alexanderplatz was both chaotic and congested with an estimated number of 3500 vehicles and 150 trams crossing it per hour. Thus a final traffic solution for Alexanderplatz was put forward in 1964 consisting of 4 junctions arranged in various levels, an underground intersection off Alexanderstrasse and pedestrian zones.

The *Zentrale Achse* was to be the nerve point of the new political and administrative centre of *Berlin Hauptstadt der DDR* where the highest and most representative buildings were to be located at Marx-Engels-Platz/Alexanderplatz. The dominant feature of the *Zentrale Achse* was its highly centralized structure and the monumental scale of its buildings and public open spaces. It was divided into three main sectors: Unter den Linden, Marx-Engels-Platz/Alexander Platz, and from Alexander Platz to Strausberger Platz, on Karl-Marx-Allee. In the political forum or the political centre of East Berlin were placed the main buildings of the DDR government designed according to Modernism, such as the *Ministeriums für Auswärtige Angelegenheiten*, the Foreign Ministry Building and the *Palast der Republik* both designed by Josef Kaiser, and the *Staatsratsgebäude*, the Council of State Building by Roland Korn and Hans-Erich Bogatzky.

Alexanderplatz, as it is *still* seen today, apart from being a strategic traffic intersection for East Berlin, shows an important part of the DDR architectural, urban, social and political history which goes beyond simplistic aesthetical appreciations. Its built form and urban ensembles depict the consolidation of the drastic shift towards industrialization, rationalization and prefabrication, which marked the return to Modernism in the DDR. This process was initiated with the *Haus des Lehrers* and *Kongresshalle*, by Hermann Henselmann, the first buildings constructed at Alexanderplatz, and with the second part of the Karl-Marx-Allee (from Alexander Platz to Strausberger Platz). There, instead of a ceremonial axis spelling the anachronic eclecticism of the reactionary Socialist Realism, a large housing state was built consisting of 14.500 dwellings, schools, cin-

emas, hotel, shops and facilities designed according to Modern architectural vocabulary and constructed in prefabricated slabs of concrete (*Platten*) with unadorned and standard elements. Buildings such as Kino Kosmos (1962), Kino International (1963), Café Moskau (1964) and the Interhotel Berolina (1963) by Joseph Kaiser, are representative architectural landmarks of this period.

The main concept underlying the redesigning of Alexanderplatz was to create a monumental ensemble conceived as a planned unity to be the centre of social life for Eastern Berliners, with new uses and functions combining traffic connections with representative and prestige buildings such as:

the *Centrum-Warenhaus* (central department store), the biggest in the hole DDR, a project of Josef Kaiser and associates from 1967-70, with fifteen thousand square metres and two thousand working-places;

the *Interhotel Stadt Berlin* (a project from 1970 by R.Korn and associates, with 39 stories and 123,2 metres high, one thousand rooms, conference halls, restaurants and many other facilities;

the *Haus der Elektroindustrie*, a building complex of 10 stories designed by H.Mehlan and associates in 1969 providing 2700 working places;

the *Haus des Berliner Verlags*, from 1970-73, designed by K.-E.Swora and associates, with 17 stories and a programme which included studios, photographic laboratories, conference halls, cafés, press centre, among other facilities; and

the *Haus der Statistik*, a project from 1968-70 by M.Hörner and associates, with 11 stories and 2700 working places. (Schulz and Gräbner: 1974)

Architecture was also integrated with the work of many artists who created some celebrated symbols of Alexanderplatz, namely the coloured frieze of the *Haus des Lehrers* and the copper relief of the *Haus des Reisens* (recently removed), both by W. Womacka, the *Brunnen der Völkerfreundschaft*, a large sculpture-fountain and the 10-metre-high *Urania-Weltuhr*, a World Clock by E.John, erected in the large open spaces of the pedestrian zone of the square.

Alexanderplatz became very attractive for Eastern Berliners with its cultural and leisure facilities, despite the criticism of some architects and planners regarding its vast urban scale. According to Dorothea Tscheschner⁴ (1993), Alexanderplatz became a centre in the daily life of the East Berlin population.

"Alexanderplatz soon developed a magical attraction for the population after the dead years of construction... Unfortunately, many people erroneously believe that this „display of strength“ in developing Alexanderplatz, following the construction of Stalinallee, met with displeasure

or rejection on the part of the populace; rather the opposite was true...the completion of Alexanderplatz was something which people wanted to be proud of. They also saw in the „familiar“ spaciousness of all the new [housing] estates a sign of the „progress“ of city planning, which was associated with more sun, air and green areas, and by no means „retrogression or even destruction of the city“.

Between Marx-Engels-Platz and Alexanderplatz, the *Fernsehturm*, a 350-metre-high television tower with a panoramic restaurant based on a project of Hans Henselmann would become the symbolic and dominant landmark of East Berlin overlooking the entire city, being visible from many parts of West Berlin, thus accentuating the ideological confrontation with the *Bundesrepublik Deutschland*. The television tower was a striking component of the new centre of East Berlin, concluded in 1969, in time for the celebration of the 20th anniversary of its foundation.

Alexanderplatz in Reunited Germany.

As soon as 1992, the Berlin government started the restoration of Peter Behrens' buildings at Alexanderplatz, the Berolina and Alexanderhaus. (Pysall: 1998) This was followed by the preparations of a restricted competition on the overall planning concept for its redevelopment, introducing a co-partnership between private investors and the city's government. This proved to be a very profitable financial operation as the Berlin government will have to spend a mere DM19 millions, less than 20% of the total costs (DM140 million) of Alexanderplatz's total redevelopment. The private investors will be responsible for DM119 million, which includes design and building construction, infrastructure, landscape architecture, playgrounds and *kindergarten*. In 7 June, 1994, the *Berliner Senat* issued the *Senatbeschuß nr.4835/94*, a resolution approving the proposal of Hans Kollhoff, as the guidelines for the redesign of Alexanderplatz, which was to be turned into a "people's place", aimed at using Berlin's most important traffic junction to bring other functions and uses to what they called, an "overdimensioned" area. (*Senatsverwaltung für Stadtentwicklung Berlin*: 2000)

A laconic explanatory report by Hans Kollhoff totally ignored the architecture urban design of Alexanderplatz carried out in the DDR, only mentioning Peter Behrens' buildings as a reference for the new architectural structures facing directly the square, which will be limited to 36,7 metres high. The main concept underlying the redevelopment of Alexanderplatz was the alleged reference to Berlin's 1920s urban fabric consisting of large and homo-

geneous block-structures, clearly showing a selection of a certain period of history to the detriment of others. In addition to this: "On the side facing away from the square, slender towers will grow out of the block-structures. They will be a second row of buildings which will mark the city skyline". (Kollhoff: 1994)

Kollhoff's argument is "taking into account the historical remains". Which historic remains? Isn't the architecture and urban design carried out during the DDR regime also historic?

A completely new built form mostly consisting of 150-metre-high skyscrapers is superimposed on the pre-existing building fabric of Alexanderplatz with mixed-use functions combining residential areas, offices, hotels, cultural and leisure facilities, restaurants, bars, etc. and calling for the demolition of the *Interhotel Stadt Berlin*, the *Haus der Elektroindustrie*, the *Haus des Berliner Verlags*, the *Haus der Statistik* and the *Haus des Reisens*. The only building to be preserved from demolition is the *Centrum-Warenhaus*, renamed *Kaufhof*, but moved to the south of the square and deprived of its urban and architectural context.

Kollhoff's project remarks shows little deference for the meaning of the pre-existing built environment of Alexanderplatz: "We would like to conclude with a **sentimental proposal**. It is to reconstruct the Berolina statue opposite the international clock, which would of course remain preserved".

This is rather a *caricatural* proposal. The reconstruction of the Berolina statue is anachronistic and turns a legitimate symbol of Berlin's past into a mere pastiche. Besides, the international clock, the *Uhrwelt*, was part of the overall Alexanderplatz urban space developed in the DDR period spelling out Modernism, and not an isolated piece of cosmetic design. It had, and it still has, an important meaning to Eastern Berliners.

Final Remarks

According to Rapoport (1990), capital cities exhibit the greatest urban design, spaces and buildings, being a center of rituals and ceremonies to communicate power and authority. Furthermore, when a new ruler, religion or ideology arises, new capitals are often formed with a new physical expression. This is also true in the replanning of Berlin as the capital of a reunited Germany, namely in the process of transition from Socialism to Capitalism in East Berlin, the former capital of the German Democratic Republic, the *Hauptstadt der Deutsche Demokratische Republik*.

In Berlin, a dramatic and politicized urban landscape has been produced in which many symbols representative of the former DDR régime have been changed or removed such as the old names of build-

ings, statues, streets and squares (e.g. the *Leninplatz*⁵, in Berlin, became *Platz des Vereinten Nationen* and the Lenin statue removed in 1992)⁶. In addition to this, some buildings have been destroyed (e.g. the *Ministeriums für Auswärtige Angelegenheiten*, the Foreign Ministry Building, in Berlin, demolished in 1995). In 1993, the Berlin government ordered the *Palast der Republik* at Marx-Engels-Platz to be leveled and a campaign to replace it with a grotesque replica of the Hohenzollern Royal Palace (whose ruins were demolished in 1950 by the DDR government) launched. Wide protests from former DDR citizens prevented the demolition of the *Palast der Republik* and polemic and controversial discussions involving historic preservation, national identity, architectural aesthetics and symbolism carries on until today.

In December 1992, the *Bundesbauministerium* recommended the demolition of the *Staatsratsgebäude*, the Council of State Building, to make way for the new Foreign Ministry Building in the *Spreeinsel*. The outcry of more of 100 German architects, planners, historians and preservationists prevented its destruction. As stated by Cornelius Hertling, the President of the Berlin Chamber of Architects:

"We find inadmissible that buildings that have become a part of urban history are being wiped out especially because they convey burdened memories. This means to erase history and identity". (Quoted in Baumeister, Bodenschatz and Günter: 1995)

The *Staatsratsgebäude*, a steel and glass structure which incorporated a baroque portal of the Royal Palace into its main facade is very representative of the early DDR's Modernism, being the first and the most important building of the régime, therefore strongly loaded with undesirable and troubled past experiences. Accordingly, the Building Commission at the *Deutscher Bundestag* (1994) did not understand the reasons to preserve the *Staatsratsgebäude* as "it was the seat of the second dictatorship in the German soil in this century". As Michael Wise (1998: 119) argues: "Destroying the East Germany remains was seen as a step toward expunging the evil of communism itself."

The incorporation of DDR listed architecture and urban design developments into the new *Denkmalliste des Landes Berlin* enacted in 1995 have aroused further polemic discussions in the *Berliner Parliament* as well as in society. Political, aesthetic and economic reasons are some of the arguments of those against the preservation of the DDR legacy such as the Karl-Marx-Allee. If the Karl-Marx-Allee is protected today it is mainly due to the last spec-

tacular action of the DDR régime which granted its preservation in 1990, just days before the reunification of Germany, under the *Denkmalpflegegesetz der DDR* (1975).

In 1995, the *Deutsche Nationalkomitee für Denkmalschutz*, issued a document called *“Nicht vergessen, sondern schützen und aufheben! Für die Erhaltung von Architektur und Städtebau der DDR “* (Do not forget, do protect and keep! For the preservation of architecture and urban developments of the DDR), which recommended the preservation of the DDR recent urban and architectural history. Its arguments were very clear:

“We should accept the DDR period as representative of the urban and architectural period of recent Germany, as a document of the Socialist architectural culture in which important buildings are representative of the DDR State and society“. (Haspel, 1997: 122-123)

Despite such efforts, Alexanderplatz, the heart of the capital of the former German Democratic Republic will be razed. As in Potsdamerplatz, powerful private investors bought a very large and strategic area of Berlin, taking over a symbolic and public territory in which a relevant part of German history was written, turning it into a private and banal theater of consumerism, and forging an artificial life carefully planned, programmed and managed to the entrepreneurial success. A millionaire undertaking of private capital that through spectacular architectures seduces society, exploiting the already dramatic history of Berlin, its tragedies and myths. In fact, the image marketing and the use of the meaning of the place reveals the powerful manipulation of the private investors to create ideal sceneries for consumerism whose historic references are merely rhetorical. Alexanderplatz/Marx-Engels-Platz should be preserved as an important piece of the urban and cultural identity of the former capital of the German Democratic Republic which combines its built environment with its complex urban functions, however vast or “overdimensioned”. Monumentality is a characteristic of capital cities despite any ideology or political systems (e.g. Brasília, Washington D.C., Canberra). (Cavalcanti: 1994)

What is the difference between the so-called totalitarian Socialist planning and the totalitarian Capitalism which privatizes a huge memorial space in the heart of a solid and democratic Germany in the beginning of the 21st century? Today the ideological confrontation of the Cold War is over. The confrontation is economic. Therefore, many authors refer to the reunification of Germany as an annexation of the territories of the former DDR.

Post-Conference Note

After the presentation and discussion of this paper at the Sixth International DOCOMOMO Conference in Brasília, a letter of formal protest against the destruction of Alexander Platz was signed by 97 architects, planners and students from all over the world participating in the Conference. The original document was sent to the *Staatssekretär, Senatsverwaltung für Stadtentwicklung, Umweltschutz und Technologie - Berlin-Mitte*, with copies to the *Architektenkammer Berlin, Landesdenkmalamt Berlin, Docomomo Germany*, and to Prof. Hans Kollhoff, the author of the Alexanderplatz project. In addition, copies of this document were sent to a number of German academics and to the main newspapers and architectural magazines in Germany.

There was no answer or comments whatsoever.

Fig. 1 – View of Alexanderplatz from 1973, from the *Fernsehturm* (Television Tower). On the right side, the Karl-Marx-Allee with the later architectural developments spelling out modernism. In the foreground, the *Centrum-Warenhaus* and the *Alexander and Berolina Haus* by Peter Behrens. Source: Landesbildstelle Berlin

Fig. – 2 View of the Karl-Marx-Allee from Hotel Stadt Berlin, at Alexanderplatz, in 1971. On the right side, the buildings of the *Haus des Lehrers* and *Kongresshalle* by Hermann Henselmann. Source: Landesbildstelle Berlin

Fig. 3 – Alexanderplatz in 1973 during the festivities of the 10th *Weltspiele der Jugend und Studenten*. A lively centre in the daily life for Eastern Berliners. In the middle, the *Brunnen der Völkerfreundschaft*.
Source: Landesbildstelle Berlin

Fig. 4 – *Haus des Lehrers* by Hermann Henselmann at Alexanderplatz in 1981 and the pannel of ceramic and metal elements by Walter Womacka.
Source: Landesbildstelle Berlin

Fig. 5 – Alexanderplatz in 1985 with the *Urania-Weltuhr*, the World Clock by E. John and the building of the *Haus des Reisens*.
Source: Landesbildstelle Berlin

Fig. 6 – The project of the new Alexanderplatz by Hans Kollhoff. On the left side, the *Fernsehturm* (Television Tower). The shaded buildings are the new architectural structures proposed to replace the pre-existing buildings. The Alexander and Berolina Haus by Peter Behrens indicated in light countours, are to be preserved.
Source: *Alexanderplatz. Städtebaulicher Ideenwettbewerb*. Ernst & Sohn. Berlin with some sketches from the author.

NOTES

¹ Albert Abela Ameropa Ltd. Jersey, EUWO-Gruppe Berlin, Deutsche Interhotel Berlin GmbH, G+J Pressehaus am Alex GmbH & Co., Kaufhof Holding AG, Liegenschaftsgesellschaft der Treuhandanstalt mbH and TERRENO.

² For instance: Martin Wagner's street plan of 1931, the allied air raid of 1945, the Socialist reconstruction during DDR régime, and the project of Hans Kollhoff, which resulted from an international competition launched in 1992, coordinated by the *Senatsverwaltung für Stadtentwicklung und Umweltschutz* (the Senate Urban Development and Environmental Protection Department).

³ As this paper is focused on the post-war Modernist developments carried out in Alexanderplatz as a fundamental part of the overall plan for the reconstruction of East Berlin, the capital of DDR, its scope does not allow further discussion on the main factors of its urban and architectural history.

⁴ Dorothea Tscheschner was a city planner in East Berlin for 30 years and has published many articles about the planning and reconstruction of East Berlin, as the capital of the DDR.

⁵ A representative example of post-war reconstruction in Berlin, *Leninplatz*, today, *Platz des Vereinten Nationen*, by H. Henselmann and H. Mehlan (Fig.), was protected for being a prototype of the industrialized buildings in Germany and, as Haspel (1998b: 27) states, a landmark of "DDR-Architekturmoderne".

⁶ Since 1990, this process has also occurred in many other cities of the former DDR (e.g. the *Olga Benario-Prestes Schule*, in Bernburg, is again called *Goethe Schule* and the *Karl-Marx Stadt*, renamed Chemnitz).

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- PhD in urban reconstruction and autocratic regimes at Oxford Brookes University and specialist in architectural and urban conservation at ICCROM-Rome. Areas of research involve in particular politics & architecture with emphasis to Eastern European cities, and vernacular architecture. Coordinator of Folk Architecture (Project Brazil-500 Years of Architecture) and lecturer at the Internationale Frauen Universität, Kassel.